

Vibrational Mode Evolution in WSe₂ under Pressure: Thermodynamic Insights from Grüneisen Parameters

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Abstract

In this work, we investigate the evolution of the Raman-active modes of bulk WSe₂ under hydrostatic compression up to 8 GPa. The in-plane E_{2g}¹ and out-of-plane A_{1g} modes both exhibit linear shifts with pressure, from ~253 cm⁻¹ to ~265 cm⁻¹ and from ~258 cm⁻¹ to ~271 cm⁻¹, respectively, highlighting the responses of intra- and interlayer bonds to compression. Analysis of these spectroscopic shifts yields mode-specific Grüneisen parameters of $\gamma(E_{2g}^1) = 0.51 \pm 0.02$ and $\gamma(A_{1g}) = 0.53 \pm 0.02$, providing a mode-weighted average $\langle \gamma \rangle = 0.524 \pm 0.015$, in close agreement with the estimated thermodynamic Grüneisen parameter $\gamma_{th} = 0.65 \pm 0.02$. Using $\langle \gamma \rangle$ and previously reported bulk and shear moduli of WSe₂ at ambient pressure, its thermal-shock resistance was estimated to be in the range of typical semiconductors and highly covalent thermal-shock-resistant ceramics. Our results provide quantitative insight into the vibrational behavior of WSe₂ under high pressure.

Keywords: tungsten diselenide (WSe₂), Raman spectroscopy, high pressure, Grüneisen parameter, thermal-shock resistance.

1. Introduction

Layered transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) such as tungsten diselenide (WSe₂) have attracted considerable attention due to their diverse and highly tunable physical properties [1–4]. In the bulk form, WSe₂ is a semiconducting material with an indirect band gap of ~1.2 eV, while monolayer WSe₂ exhibits a direct band gap of ~1.65 eV [5], making it especially attractive for applications in flexible optoelectronics [6,7], photovoltaics [8], and nanoelectronics [9]. The layered structure, held together by weak van der Waals interactions [10,11], allows for efficient intercalation [12], exfoliation [13], and strain engineering [14], enabling the manipulation of optical, and vibrational responses through external stimuli such as electric field, strain, pressure and temperature.

Hydrostatic pressure is a precise and effective means of tuning structure and physical properties of any solid, but has a pronounced effect for layered materials, allowing for continuous modulation of interatomic distances without changing chemical composition [15]. In WSe₂, pressure has been shown to significantly alter the electronic band structure, leading to a continuous band gap narrowing [16] and smooth changes in electron transport behavior [17]. For example, earlier studies have reported an iso-structural phase transition beginning at 28.5 GPa and associated with metallization at high pressures (HPs) without a change in lattice symmetry [18]. However, below this pressure, the crystal structure of WSe₂ evolves continuously with no abrupt changes in lattice or structural parameters. Only a smooth but anisotropic compression of the hexagonal lattice was detected, with the *c*-axis being significantly more compressible than the *a*-axis [18,19]. More recently, superconductivity has been observed in twisted bilayer WSe₂ [20,21] as well as in crystals of 2M WSe₂ pressurized to 4.3 GPa and cooled to 4.7 K [22], further highlighting the importance of compression in modulating the electron–phonon coupling in these materials. Despite these recent developments, an understanding of how lattice vibrational modes evolve under pressure, particularly in bulk or polycrystalline samples, remains limited. Raman spectroscopy, as a non-destructive probe of phonon behavior, offers a direct route to accessing such information [23–25], yet pressure-dependent studies of WSe₂ that reveal

lattice vibrational response, mode-specific Grüneisen parameters, and related thermodynamic implications below 10 GPa are still lacking. Such insights are particularly important for device fabrication, since the anharmonic lattice response directly influences thermal transport, energy dissipation, and structural stability under operating stress, which in turn determines the reliability of WSe₂-based technologies for flexible electronics, optoelectronics, and pressure-sensitive devices [2,3,26].

In this study, we investigate the HP vibrational behavior of bulk WSe₂ up to 8 GPa using Raman spectroscopy under hydrostatic compression. The choice of pressure range is intended to probe the intrinsic lattice response in the elastic compression regime, where the crystal structure remains stable and undergoes continuous, anisotropic compression without structural phase transitions. In this regime, bulk WSe₂ retains its semiconducting character, enabling a direct and quantitative determination of phonon anharmonicity and lattice compressibility. In contrast, at higher pressures where phase transitions or metallization occur, changes in bonding, symmetry, and electronic structure can obscure the intrinsic lattice response. Therefore, focusing on the elastic compression regime enables reliable determination of thermodynamic and mechanical properties under conditions relevant to practical applications, where materials are typically subjected to moderate, reversible stresses [14, 20, 22]. Lorentzian fitting of the first-order Raman-active modes allowed us to quantitatively resolve the evolution of the in-plane (E_{2g}^1) and out-of-plane (A_{1g}) phonons with pressure. Both modes exhibit linear shifts from which mode-specific Grüneisen parameters are derived. The mode-weighted average of these Grüneisen parameters is then compared with the thermodynamic Grüneisen parameter, revealing consistent trends in lattice anharmonicity and compressibility. By further combining the vibrational parameters with reported elastic moduli [27], we estimate the thermal-shock resistance ratio of bulk WSe₂. Our results demonstrate that the interplay between strong in-plane covalent bonds and weaker interlayer van der Waals forces dictates the lattice response under compression, offering quantitative insight into the thermomechanical robustness of WSe₂ for potential applications. Overall, our study provides valuable insight into the behavior of TMDs under HP and highlights the effectiveness of Raman spectroscopy in detecting subtle vibrational signatures associated with emerging physical phenomena.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Samples preparation

Tungsten(IV) selenide (WSe_2) powder with 99.8% purity (HQ Graphene) was used in this study. For the ambient-pressure reference measurements, the powder was placed on a standard microscope slide, while for the HP experiments it was loaded into a diamond anvil cell (DAC), as shown in Fig. 1. A typical DAC permits generation of static pressures of several dozens of gigapascals by compressing a micron-sized sample between the flattened tips (culets) of two opposing gem-quality diamonds [28]. Its compatibility with advanced optical spectroscopy and X-ray-based techniques allows for *in situ* investigation of materials' behavior under HP [29,30]. The WSe_2 powder was loaded into the sample chamber of the DAC. The chamber was prepared by pre-indenting a 250 μm -thick stainless steel gasket to a thickness of 60 μm and then drilling a central hole of 120 μm in diameter to confine the sample. A small ruby grain ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) was also placed in the chamber for *in situ* pressure measurement via the ruby fluorescence method [31]. The remaining volume was filled with a methanol–ethanol mixture in a 4:1 volume ratio as a pressure-transmitting medium to ensure hydrostatic conditions throughout the investigated pressure range [32,33].

Fig. 1. Images of the WSe_2 samples. (a) On a microscope slide. **(b)** Inside a DAC, with the sample chamber in the middle, containing the sample and the pressure transmitting medium.

2.2 Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was performed using a LabRAM HR Evolution Confocal Raman Microscope (LabRAM HR; HORIBA FRANCE SAS, Lille, France). A solid-state near-IR laser generating at $\lambda=785$ nm was used as the excitation source, providing strong Raman signal from WSe₂ and enabling the detection of second-order Raman modes [34–36]. We note that no ruby fluorescence was detected at this wavelength due to the low photon energy of the laser used [37]. Therefore, a doubled-frequency Nd:YAG 532 nm laser generating at the wavelength of $\lambda=532$ nm was employed to excite the ruby fluorescence peaks, which shift on compression allowed accurate pressure determination. Consequently, each spectroscopic measurement at every pressure point involved two steps: (i) pressure determination via ruby fluorescence using the 532 nm laser, followed by (ii) acquisition of the WSe₂ Raman spectrum using the 785 nm laser. The objective lens used for all the measurements was a custom-made 4× (NA 0.25). Finally, 3 accumulations per point and an acquisition time ranging from 5 to 25 s were employed for the Raman spectral signal.

3. Results and discussion

In this work, bulk (powder) samples were used to probe the intrinsic vibrational response of the material under hydrostatic compression. Although atomically thin layers of WSe₂ are of great interest for device applications [4, 7, 9], their Raman spectra are often influenced by substrate-induced strain, interfacial effects, and environmental perturbations [35, 36]. These effects can significantly shift phonon frequencies and obscure the intrinsic lattice dynamics. In contrast, bulk samples measured under hydrostatic conditions provide a more reliable representation of the inherent vibrational properties of the material [2, 5, 34]. Establishing such a baseline is essential for meaningful comparison with few-layer and monolayer systems. In the Raman spectrum of bulk WSe₂ at ambient conditions (Fig. 2a), two prominent spectral features are observed: a sharp peak at 246 cm⁻¹ and a broader band centered around ~260 cm⁻¹. To understand the origin of these modes, it is important to consider the crystal structure and lattice vibrational symmetry of WSe₂. WSe₂ is a layered TMD consisting of hexagonally arranged tungsten atoms sandwiched between two layers of selenium atoms [38]. Within each monolayer, tungsten atoms are coordinated in a trigonal prismatic geometry by six selenium atoms, forming strong covalent W–Se bonds within the plane. The layers are stacked along the crystallographic c-axis and held together

by weak van der Waals interactions, which allows for easy mechanical exfoliation into few- or single-layer sheets [13,39]. At ambient conditions, bulk WSe₂ crystallizes in the hexagonal 2H polytype (space group P6₃/mmc) [18,19,40], whose symmetry is described by the D_{6h}⁴ point group. This symmetry determines the allowed vibrational modes at the Γ point, expressed as $\Gamma = A_{1g} + 2A_{2u} + B_{1u} + 2B_{2g} + E_{1g} + 2E_{1u} + E_{2u} + 2E_{2g}$. where the A and B modes involve out-of-plane vibrations and the E modes correspond to in-plane vibrations [18,36,41].

Based on this classification, the observed sharp peak at 246 cm⁻¹ (see Fig. 2a) corresponds to a combination of the first-order E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes, which originate from in-plane vibrations of tungsten and selenium atoms moving in opposite directions within the basal plane (E_{2g}¹) and out-of-plane vibrations of selenium atoms along the crystallographic *c*-axis (A_{1g}), respectively [36]. A broader feature centered around ~260 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the second-order Raman mode known as 2LA(M), the overtone of the longitudinal acoustic phonon branch at the M point [36]. Such second-order modes arise from two-phonon scattering processes within the interior of the Brillouin zone, or from processes involving one phonon combined with defect-assisted scattering [34]. The observed spectral shape and position of these characteristic peaks are in good agreement with previously reported Raman spectra of WSe₂ at atmospheric pressure [34–36,39,42].

Fig. 2. Raman spectra of WSe₂. (a) Comparison of spectra at ambient pressure and at 1.2 GPa. (b) Spectra recorded at different pressure values.

Upon applying pressure up to 1.2 GPa, the E_{2g}^1 and A_{1g} modes become partially distinguishable, both, however, still contribute to a single composite spectral feature, which is shifted to the higher frequency of $\sim 258 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ when compared with its original ambient-pressure position (see Fig. 2a). This shift in the vibrational frequency is consistent with the expected lattice stiffening under compressive strain. Generally, the pressure-induced increase in phonon frequencies can be explained by the reduction of interatomic distances, which enhances the restoring forces acting on the vibrating atoms [43]. In our case, compression decreases the lattice parameters both in-plane (a -axis) and out-of-plane (c -axis), leading to stronger covalent bonding interactions between tungsten and selenium atoms within the basal planes as well as between adjacent layers along the c -axis [18,19]. With further compression up to 8 GPa, two peaks are no longer resolved, and the spectrum is dominated by a single broad peak that continues to shift toward higher frequencies, reflecting the progressive stiffening of the W–Se lattice (see Fig. 2b). Moreover, the broadband feature assigned to the 2LA(M) mode at ambient pressure (see Fig. 2a) disappears under compression, which can be attributed to pressure-induced changes in the acoustic phonon dispersion that suppress the efficiency of the two-phonon scattering process [44]. This effect is particularly pronounced in layered materials such as WSe₂, where compression enhances interlayer coupling and improves lattice ordering, thereby

limiting the disorder-assisted scattering channels that typically contribute to second-order Raman features [18].

To elucidate the evolution of the vibrational modes of WSe₂ under HP, a Lorentzian fitting of the composite peak at each pressure point was performed (see Fig. 3a). This approach allowed decomposition of this broad spectral feature and provided the positions of the E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes at each pressure while accounting for minor variations in overall peak shape. The resulting pressure dependences are presented in Fig. 3b, showing a quantitative view of the phonon frequency shifts throughout the compression range.

Fig. 3. Raman spectroscopic analysis of WSe₂ under compression. (a) Example of Lorentzian fitting of a composite Raman peak (E_{2g}¹ + A_{1g}) at 3.2 GPa. The shoulder reflects contributions from second-order and combination Raman scattering processes [18]. (b) Evolution of the E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} mode positions in WSe₂ obtained from the fitting as a function of applied pressure. Dashed

lines indicate linear fits. Insets illustrate the vibrational Raman modes, with dotted lines denoting the weak van der Waals bonds between adjacent layers.

At 1.2 GPa, the E_{2g}^1 and A_{1g} modes are located at frequencies of $\sim 253 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 258 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, and both gradually shift to higher frequencies upon increasing pressure, reaching $\sim 265 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 271 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 8 GPa. Linear fits to the experimental frequencies between 1 GPa and 8 GPa yield pressure coefficients of $1.82 \pm 0.07 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{GPa}$ for E_{2g}^1 and $1.91 \pm 0.07 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{GPa}$ for A_{1g} . The slightly larger slope of the out-of-plane A_{1g} mode indicates that it is more sensitive to compression along the c -axis compared to the in-plane E_{2g}^1 mode. Absence of any singularity in the pressure dependences of the Raman frequencies of both modes is consistent with previous studies showing that bulk WSe_2 does not undergo any structural phase transition below 28.5 GPa [18] but the hexagonal lattice exhibits anisotropic compression [18,19]. The c -axis, determined by the relatively weak van der Waals interactions between adjacent Se–Se planes, is initially more compressible than the in-plane a -axis. As the pressure increases, the Se layers are brought closer together, and the repulsive interactions between Se atoms strengthen. Over time, these repulsive forces become comparable to the W–Se intra-layer bonds, reducing the rate of the c -axis contraction. The observed linear upshift of the E_{2g}^1 and A_{1g} modes captures this interplay between intra- and interlayer forces, with the in-plane E_{2g}^1 mode reflecting stiffening of W–Se bonds and the out-of-plane A_{1g} mode directly probing the evolving interlayer interactions. Together, the pressure-dependent behavior of these modes provides a clear fingerprint of the anisotropic lattice response in bulk WSe_2 .

To further quantify the vibrational lattice response of WSe_2 under pressure, we calculated the mode-specific Grüneisen parameters for the two Raman-active vibrations, the in-plane E_{2g}^1 and the out-of-plane A_{1g} modes. We note that the Grüneisen parameter, which reflects the sensitivity of phonon frequencies to lattice compression, is a direct measure of lattice anharmonicity and provides insight into how vibrational modes respond to applied pressure [45]. The mode-specific Grüneisen parameter γ_i is defined as:

$$\gamma_i = \frac{B_0}{\omega_{0i}} \frac{\partial \omega_i}{\partial P} \quad (1)$$

Where B_0 is the bulk modulus at atmospheric pressure, ω_{0i} is the phonon frequency at a reference pressure, and $\partial \omega_i / \partial P$ is the measured pressure coefficient of the Raman mode.

Using the reported bulk modulus of bulk WSe₂ ($B_0 = 72 \pm 1$ GPa) [19] together with the measured pressure coefficients and the corresponding phonon frequencies at 1.2 GPa, we obtained $\gamma(\text{E}_{2g^1}) = 0.51 \pm 0.02$ and $\gamma(\text{A}_{1g}) = 0.53 \pm 0.02$. The difference between these values quantitatively reflects the slightly higher sensitivity of the out-of-plane mode to pressure, while the in-plane mode remains less compressible.

To provide a single representative measure of lattice anharmonicity, we calculated a mode-weighted average of the Grüneisen parameters, which accounts for the relative contribution of each phonon mode to the lattice thermodynamics. The mode-weighted average is defined as:

$$\langle \gamma \rangle = \frac{\sum_i C_i \gamma_i}{\sum_i C_i} \quad (2)$$

Where γ_i is the Grüneisen parameter of mode i and C_i is its Einstein heat capacity [46]. The Einstein heat capacity of a single mode is given by:

$$C_i(T) = k_B \frac{(\theta_i/T)^2 e^{\theta_i/T}}{(e^{\theta_i/T} - 1)^2}, \quad \theta_i = \frac{hc}{k_B} \omega_i \quad (3)$$

Where θ_i is the Einstein temperature, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light, and ω_i is the phonon frequency of the mode. It is important to note that, in our case, the E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes undergo a ~4–5 % shift between 1-8 GPa and since the Einstein temperature scales linearly with ω_i [47–49], the corresponding change in the Einstein heat capacity ($C_i(T)$) at room temperature (300 K) is ~1–2 %. Therefore, we used the frequencies of E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes at 1.2 GPa (253 cm⁻¹ and 258 cm⁻¹, respectively), to calculate the mode-weighted Grüneisen parameter for bulk WSe₂, yielding $\langle \gamma \rangle = 0.524 \pm 0.015$. We note that the use of a mode-weighted average is preferable to a simple arithmetic mean of the two γ_i values because it accounts for the relative contribution of each vibrational mode to the lattice thermodynamics. Modes with higher heat capacities exert a larger influence on the overall lattice anharmonicity, providing a more physically meaningful estimate of the material's response to pressure [50].

In addition, we calculated the thermodynamic Grüneisen parameter γ_{th} defined as:

$$\gamma_{th} = \frac{\alpha_V B_0}{\rho C_V} \quad (4)$$

Where α_V is the volumetric thermal expansion coefficient, B_0 is the bulk modulus at 1 atm, ρ is the mass density, and C_V is the specific heat per unit mass. For bulk WSe₂, we used the volumetric thermal expansion coefficient derived from the linear in-plane and out-of-plane coefficients ($\alpha_a = 5.132 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\alpha_c = 8.105 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [51] to obtain $\alpha_V = 2\alpha_a + \alpha_c = 1.84 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The specific heat was estimated from the Dulong–Petit law [52] ($C_V \approx 0.219 \text{ J g}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) with $\rho = 9.276 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ [53] and $B_0 = 72 \pm 1 \text{ GPa}$ [19]. Accordingly, the thermodynamic Grüneisen parameter is $\gamma_{\text{th}} = 0.65 \pm 0.02$. The obtained both values of the Grüneisen parameter are comparable, with the semi-theoretical thermodynamic estimate γ_{th} slightly higher than the mode-weighted Raman value $\langle \gamma \rangle$. We should note that the Raman-derived value is experimentally obtained and thus provides a direct probe of the lattice response under pressure through the measurable frequency shifts of specific optical modes. This is particularly meaningful for layered materials like WSe₂, where the out-of-plane A_{1g} mode and in-plane E_{2g}¹ mode are highly sensitive to anisotropic compression and directly capture the interplay between interlayer van der Waals forces and intralayer covalent bonding. In contrast, γ_{th} is calculated using theoretical heat capacity. It is important to note that the analysis presented in this work focuses on the two dominant first-order Raman-active modes, E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g}, which are the most prominent vibrational features in bulk WSe₂ within the investigated spectral range. The validity of this approach is supported by the good agreement between the obtained mode-weighted Grüneisen parameter and the independently estimated thermodynamic Grüneisen parameter indicating that the Raman-derived values capture the essential features of lattice anharmonicity.

Knowledge of the Grüneisen parameters enables estimation of the thermal-shock resistance of solids when their hardness or yield stress is known, as previously demonstrated for spinel-structured tin(IV) nitride [54]. The thermal-shock resistance of crystalline solids is generally governed by the interplay between their mechanical strength and their susceptibility to nonuniform thermal stresses arising from temperature gradients [55]. In ceramic systems, it has been shown that the ratio of Vickers hardness (or yield stress) to the Grüneisen parameter, H_V/γ , provides a comparative measure of thermal-shock resistance [54]. The Vickers hardness, H_V , reflects the material's resistance to plastic

deformation, while the Grüneisen parameter, γ , quantifies the lattice anharmonicity that governs thermal expansion and phonon interactions.

Although WSe₂ is not a conventional ceramic but a layered TMD, similar considerations may apply: strong in-plane covalent bonds provide mechanical stiffness, while weak interlayer van der Waals interactions result in anisotropic mechanical behavior [27]. This structural anisotropy makes WSe₂ simultaneously soft in the out-of-plane direction yet mechanically resilient within the basal planes. However, several factors must also be taken into account. Bonding anisotropy leads to mechanical responses and fracture pathways that vary with crystallographic orientation [56]. Microstructural effects, such as interlayer sliding in exfoliated or epitaxial samples, can provide additional energy dissipation not reflected in H_V [57]. Furthermore, electronic-lattice coupling, due to WSe₂'s narrow-gap semiconducting [58] and low-temperature superconducting properties [22], may influence its anharmonic response under rapid heating.

Using the experimental bulk modulus and the theoretically calculated shear modulus of bulk WSe₂ at ambient pressure ($B = 72$ GPa [19] and $G = 49.41$ GPa [27]) we estimated the Vickers hardness based on the model proposed by Chen et al. [59]:

$$H_V = 2 \left(\frac{G^3}{B^2} \right)^{0.585} - 3 \quad (5)$$

This yields $H_V \approx 9.6$ GPa, which is slightly higher than $H_V = 6.9$ GPa derived from the Mohs-scratch hardness of WSe₂ of $M=6$ [60] using the empirical formula $H_V = 3.2 \cdot M^3/100$ [61]. Combined with our experimentally determined mode-weighted Grüneisen parameter $\langle \gamma \rangle = 0.524$, we obtain $H_V/\langle \gamma \rangle$ between 13 and 18 GPa. Thus, WSe₂ exhibits a thermal-shock resistance higher than typical semiconductors such as GaAs with $H_V/\langle \gamma \rangle < 8$ GPa [54] but lower than highly covalent thermal-shock-resistant ceramics, such as β - or γ -Si₃N₄ with $H_V/\langle \gamma \rangle$ values calculated to be 34 GPa and 27 GPa, respectively [54]. This aligns with expectations from its layered structure where strong in-plane covalent bonds ensure mechanical rigidity, while weaker interlayer van der Waals interactions mitigate the lattice's response to thermal stress. Consequently, $H_V/\langle \gamma \rangle$ serves as a valuable relative figure-of-merit for WSe₂, allowing direct comparison with other solids despite its anisotropic, layered nature.

The observed anisotropic mechanical properties and relatively high thermal-shock resistance suggest that bulk WSe₂ could be a promising candidate for devices exposed to mechanical stress or rapid thermal cycling, such as flexible electronics, pressure sensors, and optoelectronic components operating at strong pulse-modulated electric currents (e.g., telecommunications) and/or under variable environmental conditions [2,3]. Furthermore, the experimentally determined Grüneisen parameters offer predictive guidance for designing WSe₂-based heterostructures and layered composites with tailored phonon-mediated thermal and mechanical properties. Overall, our results demonstrate how spectroscopic vibrational analysis can inform the rational engineering of layered materials for next-generation functional devices.

4. Conclusion

We investigated the HP vibrational mode evolution of bulk WSe₂ up to 8 GPa using Raman spectroscopy. The linear shifts of both Raman-active modes, E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g}, ranged from ~253 cm⁻¹ to ~265 cm⁻¹ and from ~258 cm⁻¹ to ~271 cm⁻¹, respectively, with pressure coefficients of 1.82 ± 0.07 cm⁻¹/GPa for E_{2g}¹ and 1.91 ± 0.07 cm⁻¹/GPa for A_{1g}. The mode-specific Grüneisen parameters were determined as $\gamma(E_{2g}^1) = 0.51 \pm 0.02$ and $\gamma(A_{1g}) = 0.53 \pm 0.02$, giving a mode-weighted average $\langle \gamma \rangle = 0.524 \pm 0.015$, while the thermodynamic Grüneisen parameter was estimated as $\gamma_{th} = 0.65 \pm 0.02$. Using the mode-weighted Grüneisen parameter together with previously reported bulk and shear moduli of bulk WSe₂ at ambient pressure, we estimated the material hardness and, consequently, its thermal-shock resistance ratio, $HV/\langle \gamma \rangle$, between 13 and 18 GPa. This places WSe₂ between typical semiconductors and highly covalent thermal-shock-resistant ceramics, highlighting its anisotropic lattice response. Our results show how the interplay between strong in-plane covalent bonds and weaker interlayer van der Waals interactions governs lattice anharmonicity and pressure response, providing quantitative guidance for designing WSe₂-based materials and devices with tailored thermal and mechanical resilience.

The present study establishes an integrated framework for bulk WSe₂ that combines vibrational, thermodynamic, and mechanical descriptions within a single consistent analysis. A direct comparison between the mode-weighted Raman-derived Grüneisen parameter and the estimated thermodynamic Grüneisen parameter enables cross-validation

of lattice anharmonicity at both microscopic and macroscopic levels, thereby strengthening the reliability of the vibrational approach. The combination of the mode-weighted Grüneisen parameter with experimentally determined elastic moduli further allows estimation of the thermal-shock resistance, linking vibrational spectroscopy directly to mechanical robustness. Together, these results demonstrate that Raman spectroscopy can serve as a practical and quantitative probe of thermomechanical properties in layered materials.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Egor Evlyukhin: Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing, Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Funding acquisition. **Klytaimnitra Katsara:** Investigation, Data curation. **Andreas Zerr:** Writing – review and editing, Methodology, Resources. **Georgios Kenanakis:** Methodology, Resources. **Ioannis Paradisanos:** Resources. **Vassilis Papadakis:** Methodology, Resources. **Pradip K. Bhowmik:** Writing – review and editing. **Emmanuel Stratakis:** Writing – review and editing, Methodology, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Resources, Project administration.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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